

Mapping sensation

Left Foot – Ramp 1 – Low

Draw where you felt the sensation.

How would you describe the sensation? Circle all that apply.

Pressure	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Twitch	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Tingling	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Touch	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Warm	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Cold	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Pain	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Electricity	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Pulsation	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

How strong was the sensation underneath the electrode?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

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Electricity	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	☒	9	10
Pulsation	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	☒	9	10

How strong was the sensation underneath the electrode?

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Mapping sensation

Left Foot – Ramp 2 – Low

Draw where you felt the sensation.

How would you describe the sensation? Circle all that apply.

Pressure	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Twitch	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Tingling	0	1	☒	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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Mapping sensation

Left Foot – Ramp 3 – Low

Draw where you felt the sensation.

How would you describe the sensation? Circle all that apply.

Pressure	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Twitch	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Tingling	0	1	☒	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Touch	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Warm	0	1	☒	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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Mapping sensation

Left Hand – Ramp 2 – Low

Draw where you felt the sensation.

How would you describe the sensation? Circle all that apply.

Pressure	0	1	☒	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Twitch	0	1	☒	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Tingling	0	1	☒	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Touch	0	1	☐	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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Pressure	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Twitch	0	1	●	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Tingling	0	1	●	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Touch	0	1	●	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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